

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY ON ULTRASONIC ASSISTED GRINDING OF C/SiC COMPOSITES

Y.C. Fu¹, H.H. Su², T. He³ and K. Ding⁴

College of Mechanical and Electrical Engineering, Nanjing University of Aeronautics and
Astronautics

Yudao Street 29, Nanjing, Jiangsu, 210016, China

¹Email: yucanfu@nuaa.edu.cn, ²Email: ssh@nuaa.edu.cn, ³Email: he-tao@foxmail.com, ⁴Email:
dkcharge@163.com

Keywords: C/SiC composites, grinding force, specific grinding energy, surface roughness, ultrasonic assisted grinding

ABSTRACT

With superior mechanical properties including low density, high wear resistance, good frictional characteristics and excellent high temperature resistance, Carbon fiber reinforced silicon carbide matrix (C/SiC) composites have been used as an excellent braking materials in aerospace industry. In the present work, ultrasonic assisted grinding (UAG) and conventional grinding (CG, without ultrasonic) tests of C/SiC composites were conducted in DMG Ultrasonic 20 Linear high speed machining center. The characteristics in UAG of C/SiC composites were studied by comparing the machining quality, grinding force, grinding force ration and specific grinding energy between the two processes. The results showed that material removal mode of carbon fiber both in CG and UAG were terraced brittle fracture, and there wasn't obvious difference in fracture size. Compared with CG, brittle fracture area of SiC is bigger during UAG. In addition, subsurface damage modes of the two processes were both brittle fracture of carbon fiber and there also wasn't obvious difference in fracture size. The surface roughness of ground surface produced by UAG was Ra 2.23~3.77 μ m, and the surface roughness Ra of ground surface produced by CG was 1.92~3.49 μ m. In comparison with CG, the normal grinding force and tangential grinding force for UAG were reduced maximally by 45%, 39% respectively of those for CG. Moreover, the grinding force ratio in UAG was 9.1-10.5 which was also lower than that in CG was 10.3-11.9. Because of lower grinding force, the specific grinding energy for UAG can decrease by 18%~39% compared to CG. Therefore, UAG can improve the grinding performance of C/SiC composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Applications of advanced ceramic matrix ceramics (CMC) have been increased in recent years. Compared with other advanced ceramics, CMC retains the desirable properties with higher fracture toughness [1]. As a typical kind of CMC, C/SiC composites possess superior mechanical properties and excellent high temperature resistance, low density, high wear resistance and good frictional characteristics [2, 3]. Because of these advantages, the C/SiC composites established as an excellent braking materials in aerospace field [4, 5].

When used as brakes or mirror surface, C/SiC components need be machined to meet the requirements of precision or surface quality [6]. Due to high hardness and brittleness, grinding with a diamond grinding wheel is main processing technology for C/SiC components. Although grinding can produce high precision and good surface integrity, Tawakoli et al. [6] found that such grain machining process produced large grinding force, force ratio and has low efficiency and high cost when it was adopted to process C/SiC composites.

Ultrasonic assisted machining was invented in 1964 as RUM for drilling holes, and it was extended to machining flat surface such as Ultrasonic Assisted Grinding (UAG) after several years of development. UAG is a kind of non-conventional machining process that it combines the material removal mechanisms of diamond grinding and ultrasonic machining [7, 8]. Many studies proved that UAG is a cost-effective approach to machine hard brittle materials such as ceramics, ceramic matrix composites and glass [9-11].

According to vibration dimension, UAG includes one-dimensional UAG and two-dimensional UAG [12, 13]. During one-dimensional UAG, the machining performance is determined by whether the vibration direction is parallel or vertical to the ground surface. Liang et al. [12] revealed that UAG can reduce the grinding forces slightly and improve the surface roughness compared with conventional grinding (CG) when the vibration direction was parallel to the ground surface. E. Uhlmann [14] conducted UAG and CG tests of advanced ceramics, and during UAG the vibration direction was vertical to the ground surface. The results suggested that UAG can reduce the grinding forces apparently without causing remarkable subsurface damage while obtaining a slight increasing ground surface roughness in comparison with CG. Similar results were also observed by Ding et al. [15] during UAG of Silicon Carbide (SiC). Zhao et al. [11] conducted many experiments to investigate the characteristics of cutting force of rotary ultrasonic machining (RUM) of K9 glass. They indicated that the maximum cutting forces of RUM are smaller than that of conventional diamond side grinding and face grinding. Therefore, UAG that possesses vibration direction vertical to the ground surface is an effective machining technology to reduce grinding force.

With an objective to improve the grinding performance of C/SiC composites, UAG and CG tests were conducted with a cup diamond wheel. The ground surface topographies, surface roughness, grinding force, grinding force ratio (ratio of normal grinding force and tangential grinding force, F_n/F_t) and specific grinding energy are compared for two processes. Based on this approach, the effect of UAG on grinding performance of C/SiC composites was studied.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2.1 Experimental setup

DMG Ultrasonic 20 Linear high speed machining center was used in the UAG and CG tests as shown in Figure 1. The ultrasonic vibration system of the machining center contains an ultrasonic generator, a tool holder and a grinding wheel. The grinding wheel is fixed on the ultrasonic tool holder, which contains a secondary coil, a piezoelectric ceramic transducer and an amplitude transformer. Along with rotation and feed motion of the grinding wheel, UAG can be executed. Shut down the ultrasonic vibration system through program when CG is conducted. Coolant is pumped simultaneously from the internal and external of the tool with wash away the swarf and keep the tool cool.

Figure 1: Experimental setup.

2.2 Experimental material

The workpiece material was C/SiC composites. As can be seen in Figure 2, the composites possess two-dimensional fabricated structure and the directions of carbon fibers contain 0° fiber and 90° fiber. In addition, it also contains SiC matrix and randomly distributed porosity. The fiber volume fraction is

about 45%. The dimensions of the workpiece were 35 mm × 8 mm × 5 mm. The workpiece was bonded to the fixture by paraffin.

Figure 2: Micro-morphology of C/SiC composites.

2.3 Grinding parameters

A sintered cup diamond wheel (Schott, Germany) was used in experiments. The outer diameter of the wheel was Ø24 mm and the wall thickness was 2 mm. The grain size was 91μm in average. Infeed grinding was adopted both in UAG and CG. Castrol emulsion was used as coolant both in all tests and concentration was about 5%. During processing, the internal coolant pressure was 10 bar and the external coolant pressure was 4 bar. The resonance frequency of the grinding wheel is 21.5 kHz and the amplitude is about 4μm. The grinding parameters are detailed in Table 1. The grinding speeds selected in the experiment were 1.26, 4.64, 8.82, 12.6 m/s. Meanwhile the federate were 50, 200, 350, 500 mm/min and the grinding depth were 5, 10, 15, 20μm. In this research, the grinding width was kept constant at 8 mm.

Tests	Grinding speed v_s (m/s)	Feed rate v_w (mm/min)	Grinding depth a_p (μm)
1	1.26	100	10
2	4.64	100	10
3	8.82	100	10
4	12.6	100	10
5	1.26	100	5
6	1.26	100	10
7	1.26	100	15
8	1.26	100	20
9	1.26	50	10
10	1.26	200	10
11	1.26	350	10
12	1.26	500	10

Table 1: Machining parameters for UAG and CG tests.

2.4 Measurement methods

The vibration frequency and amplitude of the tool end face were measured by a Polytec single-point vibrometer. Its sampling frequency was set to be 100 kHz.

Topographies of the ground surface produced during CG and UAG were observed by a Hitachi S-3400N II Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM). Due to anisotropy of C/SiC composites, the ground surface roughness R_a measured by conventional methods can not reflect ground surface morphology

characteristics. Thus arithmetic mean deviation of surface S_a is adopted and measured by Keyence VK-X100 laser microscope system. As can be seen from Figure 2, dimensions of some porosity can reach sub millimeter. If they are included in the sampling length, the results will not reflect the ground surface characteristics veritably. Thus the porosity is avoided during measurement. Carbon fiber areas vertical to each other are chosen as sampling area as illustrated in Figure 3. According to fiber dimensions in Figure 2, sampling area is $500 \times 500 \mu\text{m}^2$. The measured values shown were the average of twelve repeated measurements.

The grinding forces were measured by a Kistler four-component piezoelectric quartz crystal dynamometer (9272) and a charge amplifier (5070A).

Figure 3: Sampling area in the ground surface

2.5 Calculation of specific grinding energy

The specific grinding energy U means energy that was exhausted for removal of per unit volume material. It can reflect the mechanism associated with interaction between the grain and workpiece. U can be calculated by Eq. 1:

$$U = \frac{F_t \cdot v_s}{v_w a_p b} \quad (1)$$

where F_t is the tangential grinding force and b is the grinding width.

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Ground surface topographies

Figure 4 illustrates the typical micro-morphology of the ground surface obtained both in CG and UAG. It is found that the material removal mode of the ground surface both in CG and UAG are mainly carbon fibers fracture around the porosity (braiding angle) and terraced fracture. In addition, the fracture topographies are irregular curve. However, the fracture size of the two process have nearly no difference by comparison of the ground surface topographies. As illustrated in Fig. 4b, the terraced fracture size is about $40\sim 60 \mu\text{m}$ both in CG and UAG. Moreover, larger area fracture formed in SiC matrix resulting from hammering during UAG in comparison with CG.

(a) Micro topographies around porosities (Left: CG, Right: UAG).

(b) Terraced fracture of carbon fiber (Left: CG, Right: UAG).

(c) Micro topographies of SiC (Left: CG, Right: UAG).

Figure 4: Ground surface topographies of C/SiC ($v_s = 12.6$ m/s, $v_w = 100$ mm/min, $a_p = 10$ μ m).

3.2 Ground surface roughness

Figures 5~7 illustrate the effects of grinding speed, grinding depth and feed rate on the ground surface roughness (roughness of carbon fibers and SiC area) in UAG and CG. It is seen that the ground surface roughness does not show a stable regulation with changes in grinding speed and federate, while it increases with increasing grinding depth both in UAG and CG. In addition, it is found that UAG enlarges the ground surface roughness slightly in comparison with CG. The roughness of the ground surface produced by UAG is R_a 2.23~3.77 μ m, and the roughness of the ground surface produced by CG is R_a 1.92~3.49 μ m. This is accordance with the status of ground surface topographies shown in Figure 4.

Figure 5: Surface roughness vs. grinding speed

Figure 6: Surface roughness vs. grinding depth

Figure 7: Surface roughness vs. feed rate

3.3 Grinding force and force ratio

The grinding force graphical relationships during UAG and CG testing of C/SiC composites are shown in Figure 8. It can be seen that both the normal grinding force and tangential grinding force were lower in UAG than those in CG. In addition, the normal grinding force has a large fluctuation, especially in CG.

Figure 8: Grinding force in CG and UAG ($v_s = 12.6$ m/s, $a_p = 10$ μ m, $v_w = 100$ mm/min).

Figures 9-11 show the effect of the grinding speed, grinding depth and feed rate on the grinding force obtained in UAG and CG tests respectively. It is seen that the grinding force decreases with increasing grinding speed and increases with increasing grinding depth and feed rate both in UAG and CG. Also the grinding force in UAG is lower than those obtained in CG. The reduction percentage is maximum when grinding parameters are $v_s = 1.26$ m/s, $a_p = 5$ μ m, $v_w = 100$ mm/min, and it is 45% for normal grinding force and 39% for tangential grinding force respectively.

The value of the grinding force ratio (F_n/F_t) is determined by hardness of the workpiece and sharpness of the grinding wheel. Figure 12 presents the comparison of force ration during UAG and CG. It can be seen that the force ration are always lower than that in CG. The force ratio in UAG is about 9.1-10.5 and in CG is about 10.3-11.9 under experimental conditions. Therefore, it is easier for UAG to remove materials in comparison with CG.

Ding et al. [15] indicated that the motion trajectory of a single grain during UAG is a 3D sine curve. Figure 13 shows the interaction between the diamond grain and workpiece during UAG. Define the motion speed of the grain as v , and it can be divided into grinding speed v_s and vibration speed v_{UAG} . A motion cycle of the grain can be divided into two parts, i.e., t_1 and t_2 . During t_1 , the vibration speed v_{UAG} vertical downward to the workpiece generates the hammering on the ground surface. Compared with grinding process, hammering is easier to cause generation and expansion of cracks. Then

materials are removed. Therefore, UAG can reduce grinding force effectively. Moreover, due to more generation and expansion of cracks, elastic deformation is reduced significantly when grains penetrate into the workpiece during UAG. Thus normal grinding force is reduced simultaneously, i. e., UAG produces smaller force ration in comparison with CG. But the constant hammering also deteriorates the ground surface quality simultaneously, for example, more severe brittle fracture occurs in SiC area as shown in Figure 4(c).

Figure 9: Grinding force vs grinding speed.

Figure 10: Grinding force vs grinding depth.

Figure 11: Grinding force vs feed rate.

Figure 12: Grinding force vs feed rate Force ratio in UAG and CG.

Figure 13: Hammering and grinding processes of grains during UAG.

3.4 Specific grinding energy

Figure 14 shows the comparison of specific grinding energy during CG and UAG. Due to smaller tangential grinding force in UAG than that in CG, specific grinding energy is also smaller in UAG than that in CG under the same conditions. When the material removal rate increases from $0.008 \text{ mm}^3/(\text{mm}\cdot\text{s})$ to $0.083 \text{ mm}^3/(\text{mm}\cdot\text{s})$, specific grinding energy decreases from 15 J/mm^3 to 3.3 J/mm^3 in UAG and decreases from 24.5 J/mm^3 to 4.7 J/mm^3 . Compared to CG, the specific grinding energy for UAG can decrease by 18%-39%.

During CG of C/SiC composites, the interaction between the grains and workpiece are mainly scratching, plowing, cutting and fracturing to debris. Accordingly, grinding energy is expended by brittle fracture, plowing, ductile flow and scratching [16]. During this process, material removal is mainly by brittle fracture and ductile flow. However, most of the grinding energy is expended by ductile flow and plowing, even though material is mainly by brittle fracture. While during UAG, ductile flow and plowing decrease but brittle fracture increases, accordingly specific grinding energy decreases.

So compared to CG, UAG can reduce grinding force, force ratio and specific grinding energy without deteriorating the ground surface quality apparently. Therefore, UAG can improve the grinding performance of C/SiC composites effectively.

Figure 14: Specific grinding energy vs. specific material removal rate.

4 CONCLUSIONS

(1) Material removal mode of the ground surface both in CG and UAG are mainly carbon fibers fracture around the porosity (braiding angle) and terraced fracture. In addition, the fracture size of the two process have nearly no difference. In addition, larger area fracture formed in SiC matrix resulting from hammering during UAG in comparison with CG.

(2) The roughness of ground surface produced by UAG is Ra 2.23~3.77 μm , and the roughness of ground surface produced by CG is Ra 1.92~3.49 μm .

(3) Compared to CG, UAG can reduce grinding force and force ratio apparently. The maximum reduction percentage is 45% for normal grinding force and 39% for tangential grinding force respectively. The force ratio in UAG is about 9.1-10.5 and in CG is about 10.3-11.9 under experimental conditions.

(4) Specific grinding energy in UAG is always smaller than that in CG under the same conditions. Compared to CG, the specific grinding energy for UAG can decrease by 18%-39%.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to gratefully acknowledge the support of the Fundamental Research Funds for the Central Universities (No. CXLX11_0173).

REFERENCES

- [1] K. Fujihara, K. Ohshiba, T. Komatsu, M. Ueno, H. Ohmori and B.P. Bandyopadhyay, Precision surface grinding characteristics of ceramic matrix composites and structural ceramics with electrolytic in-process dressing, *Machining Science and Technology*, 1, 1997, pp. 81-94.
- [2] H.R. Xu, L.T. Zhang and H. Mei, The characterization of indentation of 2D C/SiC composites subjected to quasi-static indentation, *Acta Aeronauticaet Astronautica Sinica*, 33, 2012, pp. 1547-1553.
- [3] Q. Zhang, L.F. Cheng, L.T. Zhang and Y.D. Xu, Effects of interphases on thermal expansion of 3D-C/SiC composites, *Acta Aeronauticaet Astronautica Sinica*, 2, 2004, pp. 508-512.
- [4] Y.Z. Cai, S.W. Fan, H.Y. Li, L.T. Zhang, L.F. Cheng and J. Jiang, Mechanical properties of a 3D needled C/SiC composite with graphite filler, *Materials Science and Engineering, A 527*, 2010, pp. 539-543.
- [5] W. Krenkel and F. Berndt, C/C-SiC composites for space applications and advanced friction systems, *Materials Science and Engineering, A 412*, 2005, pp. 177-181.
- [6] T. Tawakoli and B. Azarhoushang, Intermittent grinding of ceramic matrix composites (CMCs) utilizing a developed segmented wheel, *International Journal of Machine Tools & Manufacture*, 51, 2011, pp. 112-119.
- [7] A. Bahman and T. Tawakoli, Development of a novel ultrasonic unit for grinding of ceramic matrix composites, *International Journal of Advanced Manufactured Technology*, 57, 2011, pp. 945-955.
- [8] N.J. Churi, Z.J. Pei, D.C. Shorter and C. Treadwell, Rotary ultrasonic machining of dental ceramics, *International Journal of Machining and Machinability of Materials*, 6, 2009, pp. 270-284.
- [9] B. Christian, S. Ralf, W. Andreas, W. Christian and H. Sophia, New systematic and time-saving procedure to design cup grinding wheels for the application of ultrasonic-assisted grinding, *International Journal of Advanced Manufactured Technology*, 47, 2010, pp. 153-159.
- [10] K. Ishikawa, H. Suwabe, T. Nishide and M. Uneda, A Study on Combined vibration drilling by ultrasonic and low-frequency vibrations for hard and brittle materials, *Precision Engineering*, 22, 1998, pp. 197-205.
- [11] C.Y. Zhao, H. Gong, F.Z. Fang and Z.J. Li, Experimental study on the cutting force difference between rotary ultrasonic machining and conventional diamond grinding of K9 glass, *Machining Science and Technology*, 17, 2013, pp. 129-144.

- [12] Z.Q. Liang, X.B. Wang, Y.B. Wu, L.J. Xie, Z.B. Liu and W.X. Zhao, An investigation on wear of resin-bonded diamond wheel in Elliptical Ultrasonic Assisted Grinding (EUAG) of monocrystal sapphire, *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, 212, 2012, pp. 868-876.
- [13] Y. Peng, Y.B. Wu, Z.Q. Liang and X. Lin, An experimental study of ultrasonic vibration-assisted grinding of polysilicon using two-dimensional vertical workpiece vibration, *International Journal of Advanced Manufactured Technology*, 54, 2011, pp. 941-947.
- [14] E. Uhlmann, Surface formation in creep feed grinding of advanced ceramics with and without ultrasonic assistance, *CIRP Annals - Manufacturing Technology*, 47, 1998, pp. 249-252.
- [15] K. Ding, Y.C. Fu, H.H. Su, X.B. Gong and K.Q. Wu, Wear of diamond grinding wheel in ultrasonic vibration-assisted grinding of silicon carbide, *International Journal of Advanced Manufactured Technology*, 71, 2014, pp. 1929-1938.
- [16] S. Malkin and T.W. Hwang, Grinding mechanisms for ceramics, *CIRP Annals - Manufacturing Technology*, 45, 1996, pp. 569-580.